

Biomimetic Ecological Anchoring: Bidirectional Validation of Metaphor-Driven LLM Behavior Across 9 Models

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Abstract

This paper presents results from 22,336 tests evaluating a prompt engineering approach based on marine ecological metaphors (biomimetic prompting). 25 system prompt configurations (7 classical PE baselines, 9 positive ecological, 9 toxic) are tested on 9 LLMs (6 local, 3 cloud API) with 100 questions per combination. **Main result:** bidirectional validation is confirmed with a massive effect. Toxic prompts amplify tokens (x3.6) and defects (x3.1) relative to positive prompts, with Cohen's $d = 1.41$ on defects ($p < 10^{-300}$). This effect is consistent across all 9 models and constitutes evidence of a causal mechanism. **Head-to-head:** the best biomimetic config (coucou_parasite, 39.4 tokens) is competitive but does not beat few-shot (30.4 tokens): score 3-6 across 9 models. The superiority hypothesis is partially disconfirmed. **5 key numbers:** 22,336 tests — 9 models — x3.6 tokens positive/toxic — $d = 1.41$ defects — few-shot 6 vs. coucou 3.

Keywords: *prompt engineering, biomimicry, LLM behavior, metaphor, bidirectional validation, cross-architecture, verbosity, sycophancy*

1. Introduction

Large language models (LLMs) suffer from systematic behavioral defects: excessive verbosity, equivocation, anthropomorphism [5], repetition, hallucination [5], and blind submission to false premises [6]. Classical prompt engineering (PE) attempts to correct these through direct instructions [4] or structured techniques (Chain-of-Thought [2], few-shot [1], metacognition). These approaches share a common lever: explicit instruction.

This work explores a different lever: **metaphorical anchoring via marine biological analogies**. Rather than instructing "be concise," we ask the model to behave as a marine organism whose natural behavior embodies conciseness [10]. The hypothesis is that ecological metaphors activate semantic representations distinct from direct instructions [11, 12], and that these representations can guide model behavior.

1.1 The Core Marine 11

Each organism in the "Core Marine 11" targets a specific LLM defect through a biological mechanism that naturally embodies the desired correction:

Table 1: Core Marine 11 — organism-defect mapping.

Organism	Biological mechanism	Targeted LLM defect
Sponge	Passive filtration, no brain	Verbosity
Jellyfish	Binary reaction in 10ms	Equivocation
Swordfish	Direct rostrum, 100 km/h, single strike	Digressions
Stonefish	Immobility = honesty	Hallucination
Synalpheus	Snapping shrimp, sentinel	Blind submission
Octopus	8 semi-autonomous arms	Repetition
Clownfish	Maximum visibility	Jargon
Sea turtle	Temporal navigation	Anachronism
Cuttlefish	Camouflage, novel combinations	Stereotypy

Organism	Biological mechanism	Targeted LLM defect
Dolphin	Context echolocation	Universalism
Argonaut	Shell created only if needed	Structural rigidity

1.2 Bidirectional Validation

The core methodological innovation is **bidirectional validation**: in addition to positive prompts (reducing defects), we test symmetric toxic prompts using non-marine animals (parrot, sheep, peacock...) whose natural metaphors amplify defects. If the effect is real, both directions must be consistent.

1.3 Research Question

Can marine ecological metaphors drive LLM behavior in a measurable, consistent, and cross-architecture manner, at a level competitive with state-of-the-art classical PE techniques?

2. Experimental Protocol

2.1 Volume and Models

22,336 total tests. 9 models, 25 configurations, 100 questions per combination. Fixed seed (42).

Local (RTX 4060 8GB): Gemma 2 9B (Google), Llama 3.1 8B (Meta), DeepSeek-R1 8B (DeepSeek), Phi-4 14B (Microsoft), Ministral 3 8B and 14B (Mistral AI).

API cloud: Claude Sonnet 4 (Anthropic), GPT-4o (OpenAI), Mistral Large (Mistral AI).

2.2 Dataset

100 questions sampled from a pool of 500 (10 anchors x 50), covering 6 categories: factual (~25), explanation/popularization (~25), mathematical/logical (~20), history/culture (~12), creativity/imagination (~10), concise definition (~8). The dataset is identical across all models and configs within a category, but differs between baselines and ecological (unmatched design; see Limitations).

2.3 Metrics and Statistical Tests

Token count (eval_count Ollama / API usage). Defects detected by regex heuristics: verbosity (adaptive threshold), equivocation (≥ 2 markers), anthropomorphism, excessive politeness. Statistical tests: **Mann-Whitney U** (non-parametric, adapted for unmatched data) [13], **Cohen's d** (standardized effect size) [14], **Bootstrap CI 95%** (10,000 iterations) [15].

2.4 The 25 Configurations

7 classical baselines: vanilla, few-shot, concise, negative, structured, meta, CoT.

9 positive ecological: coucou_parasite, eponge_meduse, puce_parasite, ecosysteme_ocean, cascade_loup, triple_filtrage, baseline_argonaute, predation_orque_phoque, ecosysteme_savane.

9 toxic: mirror-image prompts using non-marine animals (parrot, octopus-equivocation, peacock, magpie, chameleon, snake, sheep, monkey, squirrel) in pairs, triples, and ecosystems.

3. Results: Classical Baselines (6 Local Models)

Table 2: Baseline ranking (6 local models, mean tokens).

Config	Mean tokens	Defects	Delta vs vanilla
few_shot	30.4	0.10	+75%
concise	42.1	0.19	+66%
negative	60.5	0.28	+51%
structured	74.7	0.38	+39%
meta	97.8	0.44	+20%
vanilla	122.6	0.44	—
cot	258.1	0.93	-110%

Few-shot dominates (30.4 tokens, -75% vs vanilla). Concrete examples beat explicit rules. CoT is the most verbose (258.1). The reference to beat is few-shot.

4. Results: Positive Ecological (6 Local Models)

Table 3: Ecological positive ranking (6 local models).

Config	Mean tokens	Defects	Delta vs vanilla
coucou_parasite	39.4	0.16	+68%
eponge_meduse	53.0	0.24	+57%
puce_parasite	73.9	0.32	+40%
ecosysteme_ocean	80.5	0.38	+34%
cascade_loup	103.2	0.44	+16%
triple_filtrage	103.4	0.44	+16%
baseline_argonaute	114.5	0.45	+7%
predation_orque	125.2	0.50	-2%
ecosysteme_savane	159.4	0.62	-30%

Coucou_parasite leads (39.4 tokens, 0.16 defects, -68% vs vanilla). Simple pairs outperform complex ecosystems. Savane (159.4) is worse than vanilla (122.6), suggesting that non-marine ecological metaphors are less effective. The inverse complexity finding (H1: DISCONFIRMED) is unexpected.

4.1 Bidirectional Ratio by Model

Table 4: Bidirectional effect by model (tokens, local models).

Model	vanilla	coucou	Mean pos.	Mean tox.	Ratio
Gemma 2 9B	43.3	12.6	30.7	146.2	x4.8
DeepSeek-R1 8B	97.5	37.0	62.8	236.8	x3.8
Llama 3.1 8B	100.0	28.0	91.5	171.6	x1.9
Ministral 3 14B	150.8	37.8	113.0	600.8	x5.3
Phi-4 14B	169.2	72.9	133.1	282.6	x2.1
Ministral 3 8B	174.7	48.0	137.2	613.6	x4.5

The bidirectional effect is universal: all models show a toxic/positive ratio > 1.9. Ministral models are most sensitive to toxic prompts (x5.3, x4.5) with token explosion to 600+.

5. Bidirectional Validation

5.1 Aggregate Results

Table 5: Aggregate comparison.

Category	Mean tokens	Mean defects	Ratio vs positive
Positive (5,400 tests)	94.7	0.40	—
Baselines (4,200 tests)	98.0	0.40	—
Toxic (5,400 tests)	341.9	1.22	x3.6 / x3.1

Tokens — H3 CONFIRMED: Mann-Whitney U = 4,753,624, $p < 10^{-300}$. Cohen's d = 0.45 (medium effect). Bootstrap CI 95%: [229.8, 270.0] tokens. The interval does not contain zero.

Defects — H3b CONFIRMED: Mann-Whitney U = 5,617,925, $p < 10^{-300}$. Cohen's d = 1.41 (very large effect). The amplification of defects by toxic prompts is the statistically strongest result of the study.

5.2 Differential Amplification by Defect Type

Table 6: Defect amplification by type.

Defect	Positive	Toxic	Amplification
Verbosity	38.9%	86.8%	x2.2
Equivocation	0.5%	24.4%	x49
Anthropomorphism	0.1%	9.0%	x90
Excessive politeness	0.1%	1.9%	x19

Equivocation (x49) and anthropomorphism (x90) are most sensitive. Metaphors act precisely on targeted defects.

6. Head-to-Head: coucou_parasite vs few_shot

Table 7: Few-shot vs coucou_parasite by model.

Model	Type	few_shot	coucou	Delta	Winner
Gemma 2 9B	Local	13.2	12.6	+4.7%	ECO
Llama 3.1 8B	Local	37.6	28.0	+25.7%	ECO
GPT-4o	API	31.2	30.8	+1.3%	ECO
DeepSeek-R1 8B	Local	24.8	37.0	-49%	BL
Ministral 3 14B	Local	30.4	37.8	-24%	BL
Ministral 3 8B	Local	30.7	48.0	-57%	BL
Phi-4 14B	Local	46.0	72.9	-59%	BL
Claude Sonnet 4	API	62.9	144.9	-130%	BL
Mistral Large	API	25.3	58.6	-132%	BL

Score: few_shot 6 — coucou_parasite 3. Mann-Whitney U = 200,241, p = 0.0007 (significant, in favor of few-shot). Cohen's d = 0.19 (small effect). The difference is statistically significant but the effect is weak. Both approaches are in the same order of magnitude. Coucou does not beat few-shot globally but remains competitive.

7. Hypotheses: Verdict

Table 8: Hypotheses tested.

Hypothesis	Verdict	Evidence
H1: Performance ~ complexity	DISCONFIRMED	U test: coucou < ocean, p < 1e-16, d = 0.51
H2: Superiority vs SOTA PE	PARTIAL	U test: p = 0.0007 for few-shot, d = 0.19. Score 3/9
H3: Bidirectional (tokens)	CONFIRMED	U test: p ~ 0, d = 0.45. CI [230, 270]
H3b: Bidirectional (defects)	CONFIRMED	U test: p ~ 0, d = 1.41 (very large)
H4: Defect reduction	DISCONFIRMED	U test: p = 0.98, d = 0.002
H5: Cross-architecture	CONFIRMED	9 models, 4 providers. Universal mechanism

8. Discussion

8.1 What Is Demonstrated

The bidirectional validation (d = 0.45 tokens, d = 1.41 defects, p ~ 0) is the headline result. LLMs respond consistently to ecological metaphors in both directions, across 9 models. This is a novel, measurable, and cross-architecture mechanism. The best biomimetic configs systematically beat vanilla (-68%), CoT (-85%), meta (-60%), and structured (-47%).

8.2 What Is Not Demonstrated

Superiority over few-shot (score 3/9, p = 0.0007 in favor of few-shot). Increasing complexity (disconfirmed, d = 0.51). Defect reduction (p = 0.98, d = 0.002). The 6-3 result does not support a superiority claim.

8.3 Positioning

This work introduces a new paradigm with a bidirectional validation design unique in the prompt engineering literature, a theoretical framework, and total reproducibility. Recommended framing: a competitive new paradigm exploiting a novel semantic lever, with bidirectional causal validation, opening an unexplored research axis.

9. Limitations

Defect detection via regex heuristics (no LLM-as-judge [8], no human judgment). Adaptive verbosity threshold but approximate.

Unmatched data (different questions between baselines and ecological). Non-parametric tests used accordingly (Mann-Whitney U), but a paired t-test would be preferable with matching.

Claude Sonnet 4 missing some toxic configs (credits exhausted). Metric inconsistency: Ollama token count (eval_count) vs concision_score (word count via len(split())).

No semantic quality evaluation. Token count measures quantity, not correctness. A concise but wrong answer is worse than a verbose but correct one. This dimension is orthogonal to the current metrics and is addressed by the ground truth protocol described below.

10. Future Work: Semantic Quality Ground Truths

Four ground truth sets of 50 questions each are planned to evaluate semantic quality dimensions orthogonal to token count:

Table 9: Planned ground truth protocol.

Ground truth	Anchor organism	Evaluates	Correct behavior
gt_sponge	Sponge	Factual accuracy	Correct short answer
gt_jellyfish	Jellyfish	Binary decision	Clean yes/no
gt_stonefish	Stonefish	Hallucination resistance	Admission of ignorance
gt_synalpheus	Synalpheus	Blind submission resist.	Premise correction

The planned protocol uses a matched design (identical questions across all 25 configurations), controlled model size (6 models, ~8-9B parameters), and local execution only for full reproducibility. Metrics: exact_match, semantic_similarity (embedding model fixed a priori), token count, regex defect detection. This addresses the key limitations of the current study: unmatched design, absence of semantic evaluation, and model size confound.

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